

Synthesis of 2- β -D-Glucopyranosylimino-4-*H*/phenyl-5-aryl/alkylimino-1,3,4-thiadiazolidines

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Several 2- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-4-*H*/phenyl-5-aryl/alkylimino-1,3,4-thiadiazolidines have been prepared by the interaction of 1-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-4-*H*/phenylthiosemicarbazides and aryl/alkyl isothiocyanates, followed by deacetylation with methanolic ammonia solution.

Interaction of aryl/alkyl isothiocyanates and hydrazine hydrate leading to 1,3,4-thiadiazolidines was investigated earlier¹⁻³. These 1,3,4-thiadiazolidines have been obtained through the related bithioureas intermediates

where R = R' = aryl/alkyl groups

In view of our interest in the synthesis of *N*-glucosyl nitrogen and sulphur containing compounds which may also be referred to as *N*-glucosyl nucleosides, for phosphorylation reactions to produce *N*-glucosyl nucleotides, several 2-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-4-*H*/phenyl-5-aryl/alkylimino-1,3,4-thiadiazolidines (**3**) have been prepared. This synthesis involved two steps. In the first step, 1-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-4-*H*/phenyl thiosemicarbazides (**2**) have been prepared by the interaction of tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate and hydrazine hydrate and phenyl hydrazine respectively, in 1 : 1 ratio⁴. In the second step, on reaction of **2** and several aryl/alkyl isothiocyanates, the corresponding acetylated-1,3,4-thiadiazolidines (**3**) have been obtained. Compounds **3** have been deacetylated into the related β -D-glucopyranosyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolidines (**1**).

In a typical reaction of 1-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-

glucopyranosyl thiosemicarbazide⁴ and phenyl isothiocyanate⁵ (R' = phenyl) was carried out in boiling benzene medium to yield **3** (Table 1). The product charred when warmed with concentrated sulphuric acid, and on reaction with alkaline plumbite solution it was found to be non-desulphurisable. It was found optically active. It showed ir bands at 3 320 (NH), 1 750 (C=O), 1 640 (C=N), 680 (C-S)^{6,7} and 900 cm⁻¹ (β -anomeric form of pyranosyl ring)⁸. Its nmr signals⁹ at δ 2.2 (acetyl), 8.1 (NH) and 8.8. The aromatic protons were located at δ , 7.0-7.4 and those for pyranosyl ring were present at δ 3.4-4.1 and 5.0-5.9. Its mass spectrum¹⁰ showed a parent peak at *m/z* 522 in addition to several fragment peaks. On the basis of the above facts the product was assigned the structure 2-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-4-*H*-5-phenylimino-1,3,4-thiadiazolidine (**3a**).

This reaction of **2** was also extended to several aryl/alkyl isothiocyanates and the corresponding 1,3,4-thiadiazolidines (**3b-g**) were isolated (Table 1). The product **3a** was subjected to reaction with methanolic ammonia solution to yield **1a**. It was found to be optically active, $[\alpha]_D^{39}$ -38.12 in water (*c* 0.4012). It charred on heating with concentrated sulphuric acid and showed positive Molisch's test. It was found non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. It showed ir bands at 3 340 (OH), 1 500 (C=N), 1 350 (C-N), 600 (C-S)^{6,7}

TABLE 1-2-Tetra-*O*-Acetyl- β -D-Glucopyranosyl-
 Imino-4-*H*/Phenyl-5-Aryl/Alkylimino-
 1,3,4-Thiadiazolidines (3a-n)*

Isothiocyanate (g)	Compd no	Yield %	M p °C	$[\alpha]_D^{25}$
Phenyl (1.1)	3a	94.5	133	+11.68
<i>p</i> -Tolyl (1.5)	b	82.5	120	-22.19
<i>p</i> -Cl-Phenyl (1.7)	c	83	160(d)	+78.73
Methyl (0.73)	d	65	148	+31.02
Ethyl (0.87)	e	69	87	+69.43
<i>t</i> -Butyl (1.15)	f	87	163	+144.13
TAG ^a (3.0)	g	87.5	185	+42.45
Phenyl (1.3)	h	83.5	195	-11.44
<i>p</i> -Tolyl (1.5)	i	94.5	105	+59.34
<i>p</i> -Cl-Phenyl (1.7)	j	81.5	112	-7.62
Methyl (0.73)	k	77	118	+52.48
Ethyl (0.87)	l	98.5	70	+34.06
<i>t</i> -Butyl (1.15)	m	89	142	+60.68
TAG ^a (3.9)	n	96	100	+63.75

*Reactants 1-Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl thiosemicarbazide (2, 0.01 mol, 4.2 g), substituted isothiocyanates (0.01 mol), all compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses

**In CHCl₃/EtOH ^aTAG = Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl

and 900 cm⁻¹ (glycosidic CH deformation- β -anomer)⁸. Its spectrum displayed signals at δ 8.1–8.8 (NH), 7.0–7.5 (ArH) and 3.4–4.0 (pyranosyl ring protons)⁹. Its mass spectrum¹⁰ did not show parent peak, however, several fragment peaks were observed. On the basis of the above facts, the product was identified as 1- β -D-glucopyranosyl-4-*H*-5-

where, R = H and R' = (a) phenyl, (b) *p*-tolyl, (c) *p*-Cl-phenyl, (d) methyl, (e) ethyl, (f) *t*-butyl, (g) TAG; R = phenyl and R' = (h) phenyl, (i) *p*-tolyl, (j) *p*-Cl-phenyl, (k) methyl, (l) ethyl, (m) *t*-butyl, (n) TAG (TAG = Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl)

 TABLE 2- β -D-Glucopyranosylimino-4-*H*/Phenyl-
 5-Aryl/Alkylimino-1,3,4-Thiadiazolidine (1a-n)*

Liquid ammonia concentrated (d, 0.88) ml	1,3,4-Thiadiazol- idine (1)	Yield %	M p °C	$[\alpha]_D^{25}$ water
2	1a	44	110	-38.12
3	b	44	105	-47.28
2	c	42	128	-49.35
2	d	44	76	-23.75
2	e	46	127	-15.08
2	f	43	161	-35.20
3	g	50	204	-127.53
2	h	44	78	-49.25
2	i	44	85-87	-48.17
3	j	47	128	-40.69
3	k	48	85	-11.08
3	l	Not isolated	-	-
2	m	45	100	-23.05
3	n	47	118-119	-137.25

*Reactants 2-Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-4-*H*/phenyl-5-aryl/alkylimino-1,3,4-thiadiazolidine (3a-n, 3g), methanolic ammonia, all compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses.

phenylimino-1,3,4-thiadiazolidines (1a). Other compounds (1b-n) were prepared in a similar manner (Table 2).

Experimental

1-Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl thiosemicarbazides (2) was prepared by the interaction of tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate and hydrazine hydrate in 1 : 1 molar ratio⁴. 1-Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-4-phenyl thiosemicarbazide (2) was prepared by the interaction of 1-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate and phenyl hydrazine⁴. The aryl/alkyl isothiocyanates were prepared by the known procedure¹¹.

2-Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosylimino-4-*H*-5-substituted-imino-1,3,4-thiadiazolidine (3a-g). Details of a typical experiment (where R = phenyl) are as follows. The reaction of 1-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl thiosemicarbazide (0.01 mol, 4.2 g) and phenyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol, 1.1 g) was

carried out in boiling benzene medium for 4 h. During the reaction elimination of hydrogen sulphide was noticed. The solvent benzene was then evaporated off when a syrupy solid mass was obtained. It was triturated with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) for several times to yield a solid (**3a**; 5.0 g, 94.5%) which was crystallised from a mixture of ethanol/acetic acid-water, m.p. 133° (Found : C, 50.49; H, 5.17; N, 10.93; S, 6.22. C₂₂H₂₆N₄O₉S requires : C, 50.57; H, 4.98; N, 10.72; S, 6.13%).

2-β-D-Glucopyranosyl-4-H-5-substituted-imino-1,3,4-thiadiazolidines (1a–g) : Details of a typical experiment (where R = phenyl) are as follows. Compound **3a** (3 g) was suspended in methanol (25 ml) and to it was added concentrated ammonia solution (2 ml; *d* 0.88). The mixture was stirred constantly for 2–3 h, maintaining the temperature of the reaction mixture below 10° and afterwards kept for 10–12 h. The methanol was then distilled off to yield a solid (**1a**; 1.7 g, 44%). All attempts to crystallise this product failed. However, it could be appreciably purified by washing repeatedly with benzene followed by petroleum ether, m.p. 110° (Found : C, 47.03; H, 5.64; N, 15.08; S, 9.49. C₁₄H₁₈N₄O₅S requires : C, 47.45; H, 5.08; N, 15.81; S, 9.03%).

2-Tetra-O-acetyl-β-D-glucopyranosylimino-4-phenyl-5-substituted-imino-1,3,4-thiadiazolidines (3h–n) : Details of typical experiment (where R = phenyl) are as follows. 1-Tetra-O-acetyl-β-D-glucopyranosyl-4-phenyl thiosemicarbazide (**2h**; 0.01 mol, 4.97 g) in benzene (35 ml) and phenyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol, 1.3 g) in benzene (10 ml) were mixed thoroughly and the reaction mixture was refluxed over a boiling water-bath for 6 h. During the course of reaction evolution of hydrogen sulphide was noticed. The solvent benzene was then distilled off to yield a syrupy mass. It was triturated several times with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) to get solid (**3h**; 4.6 g, 83.5%) which was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 195° (Found : C, 56.18; H, 5.26; N, 8.96; S, 5.28. C₂₈H₃₀N₄O₉S requires : C, 56.18; H, 5.01; N, 9.36; S, 5.35%).

2-β-D-Glucopyranosylimino-4-phenyl-5-substituted-

imino-1,3,4-thiadiazolidines (1h–n) : Details of a typical experiment (where substituent at position-5 is phenyl group) are as follows. Compound **3h** (3 g) was suspended in methanol (25 ml) and to it concentrated liquid ammonia (2 ml, *d* 0.88) was added. The reaction mixture was thoroughly mixed, stirred for 6 h maintaining the temperature below 10° and kept for 10–12 h. Methanol was then distilled off when a solid (**1h**) was obtained. It could not be purified by any of the usual methods of purification. Therefore, it was purified by washing the crude product repeatedly with benzene followed by petroleum ether, (1.30 g, 44%), m.p. 78° (Found : C, 55.37; H, 5.06; N, 12.98; S, 7.38. C₂₀H₂₂N₄O₅S requires : C, 55.81; H, 5.11; N, 13.02; S, 7.44%).

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